

Design and testing of a 5G-enabled rural drone service

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The XGain project [1] aims to develop the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), a digital tool designed to guide rural stakeholders in selecting suitable Information and Communication Technology (ICT) infrastructures for their digital services. The suggestions produced by the KFT are based on a series of input parameters, like the region in which the service is to be deployed, weather conditions, type of service to be implemented and the devices used. The output is a variety of technological mixes and an assessment on how these mixes impact a series of techno-economic, social and ecological factors, as well as the creation of an adapted business plan canvas. The XGain project's engineers have designed the algorithms and methodologies used to process the inputs into outputs that are as useful and as close to reality as possible. One way to validate the outputs in the testing phase of the KFT is to use reference scenarios with real use cases (UCs) and infrastructure, to check if the produced outputs are close to reality and maybe either of both, the KFT or the existing deployment, need to be improved.

As part of the XGain project, six use cases evaluate how various radio and computing technology mixes can digitalize and modernize rural services. These UCs can be used as reference for the KFT. In this article we focus on the Catalonian UC that explores how a drone centre could impact on a rural community: training and educating users on the benefits of drones, their operation, and relevant regulations that affect these devices, can foster drone adoption and help close the digital gap in rural areas. Further, the drone centre would be equipped with an infrastructure for users to test their drones with state-of-the-art technology, making it much easier for farmers and other potential drone users to validate their solutions and services.

To explore the potential ICT infrastructure that would need to be present in a drone centre, it is important to understand which services would be tested/supported there. Understanding the service to be implemented allows us to extract the technical requirements of the infrastructure to support it. As such, we define a typical drone service: one where the drone flies over an area that needs to be observed or monitored. The drone uses a camera to capture objects, like crops, trees or animals and this information is transmitted for either immediate or delayed processing, e.g., using artificial intelligence (AI). For the transmission in real time, a strong connection is needed to support high-

quality videos and/or multi-camera drones. For the processing, a device with enough computing capabilities is required in order to properly process the incoming video.

The technologies chosen

After evaluating different radio technologies, like Wi-Fi, 4G and 5G, for their coverage range and performance, it was decided that the UC would feature a private 5G network. Such cellular networks guarantee a certain connectivity quality of the registered users, they provide wide range connectivity (especially compared to Wi-Fi), even with small base stations (small cells), and the capacity to carry traffic is sufficient for allowing the transmission of high-quality media or other types of heavy traffic. The 5G infrastructure uses the Cablefree 'Emerald' Small Cell, a compact base station, and the Open5GS core, which is a flexible, open-source mobile network solution.

As for the edge computing infrastructure, the selected devices are a Raspberry Pi 4 device that would be mounted on the drone, and two Next Unit of Computing (NUC) devices that would respectively host the 5G core, and the AI app that processes the incoming video. The overall setup, including how the drone communicates with the 5G network and edge computing devices, is shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1: Overall drone service setup.

The top right box represents the Drone, on which the Raspberry Pi 4 is mounted, along with a camera. The Raspberry Pi 4 is connected over a 5G CPE/modem (Comms365) to the 5G small cell, depicted in the top left corner. The small cell connects over ethernet with a NUC compute node, represented by the bottom left box, where the 5G Core runs. Finally, another NUC (bottom right) runs two applications: The video streaming app that receives the stream coming from the drone and the object detection app that relies on AI to identify different object types captured on video.

Overall, this setup allows for the live stream of video content and its processing at the edge with low latency. In the lab, we evaluate the performance achievable by the 5G network and processing devices, measuring whether the requirements of this typical drone service can be satisfied.

Measurements

In the following, we present the results for several key technical KPIs that are relevant to the service, including the latency and throughput of the 5G connection, as well as the CPU usage.

Latency/Round-trip time (RTT)

Figure 2: RTT measurements.

This measurement indicates how responsive the network is or, in other words, how fast an endpoint (in this case an edge device) can reply to requests or messages sent by clients connected to the 5G network. To obtain this RTT measurement we used the ping tool. Figure 2 provides the overview of 3 experiments running over the course of 20 minutes. This time (20 minutes) mimics a typical drone flight duration. The average RTT during the experiments was 28.775 ms. The average jitter, on these experiments, was 5.89 ms of the RTT. For the calculation of the jitter, we use the standard deviation calculated from the measured time series. This performance is in the range of a typical 5G network. Note that the one-way delay is half of the values presented in this section.

TCP & UDP Downlink

In this scenario the data was being sent from the Intel NUC to the Raspberry Pi, it is the most common communication type on cellular networks and usually the direction on which more radio resources are allocated. A 1-hour experiment was performed, and the results are shown in Figure 4. From these experiments we can observe that the average downlink throughput sticks to a relatively constant throughput of 113 Mbit/s for both TCP and UDP. The stable performance reflects the expected behaviour of the private 5G network, considering there is just a single end device in the network and dedicated spectrum is used.

Figure 3: Downlink throughput results.

TCP & UDP Uplink

The following scenario tested the throughput in the opposite direction as in scenario the previous scenario: the traffic was being sent from the Raspberry Pi to the Intel NUC. This scenario is highly relevant to the video transmission drone service used as references scenario for this UC, given the data needs to be sent from the end devices over private 5G network to the edge server. Similarly to the TCP and UDP Downlink scenario, a 1-hour experiment was performed, and the results are shown in Figure 4. The average uplink throughput on these experiments was 70Mbit/s for UDP and 77Mbit/s for TCP which is above the requirement of 20 Mbit/s needed for the transmission of a 4k streaming of a video.

Figure 4: Uplink throughput results.

Overall, the stable downlink and uplink throughput, averaging 113 Mbit/s and around 79 Mbit/s in down- and uplink, respectively, demonstrates that the private 5G network can reliably support real-time video streaming from drones, a critical requirement for drone-based services in agriculture or forestry.

Resource utilization (Near Edge - NUC)

In Figure 5, we observe the CPU and RAM histograms of the NUC, which is acting as the streaming client, and therefore, receives and processes the video from the Raspberry. Two interesting patterns are observed below.

On the CPU side, an almost undetectable usage is analysed during the entire transmission, where not even more than 1% of the total available (8 vCPUs) is consumed, being the average at 0.21%. It is a logic result, since no CPU-intensive application is running. This indicates that the device could host in parallel other computing services that through virtualization could allow the use of shared computing infrastructure for different stakeholders.

If we analyse the RAM histogram, we can see that the usage is relatively high and quite stable, where it varies between 5725 MB and 5755 MB, which is a very small variation. This is equivalent to a consumption of 70% of the total RAM. Such consumption is related with the buffering of the incoming video. Such results, serves to validate that the device can adequately handle an incoming streaming video.

Figure 5: Computing resource usage results.

Conclusions

In conclusion, by looking at the performance and capacities of the technology mix used in this typical drone scenario, it can be safely stated that an infrastructure mix that contains a 5G private network and edge computing enables plenty of scenarios, both for the implementation of a drone centre with support for state-of-the-art use cases, as well as for a high-speed Internet access for other users. It should be noted though, that for the operation of this infrastructure the necessary spectrum needs to be assigned. As part of the project, 40 MHz can be obtained from the Spanish ministry, however, for a commercial use, getting private spectrum is currently not trivial. In such a case, network operators might offer “standalone” network solutions that offer similar or even better performance (due to higher spectrum availability).

In the future, the integration of 5G and edge computing in rural areas can unlock new possibilities for modern infrastructures, like a drone operations centre, improving quality of life by bringing digitalized drone services closer to the rural areas and bridging the digital divide.

References

- [1] XGain Project, <https://kgain-project.eu/>

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